

TITLE: FREQUENCIES OF THE HEART

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Annotation: determination of heart defects, classification of heart defects, mitral valve defects.

Key words: heart defect, valve damage, syndrome, ECG, echo kg.

Congenital or acquired defects of the heart structures (valve apparatus, heart partitions, trunk vessels), leading to impaired intracardial and systemic hemodynamics.

By localization of valve lesion:

- Mitral valve defects
- aortic valve defects
- tricar valve defects
- Light artery valve defects
- complex vices (the presence of defects of several valves at once)

By the nature of the valve damage:

- stenosis (narrowing of the valve hole)
- insufficiency (incomplete closing of valve wings)
- combined (= combined) (combination on one valve of stenosis and insufficiency)

Clinical manifestations of acquired heart defects:

- valve lesion syndrome
- Syndrome of the primary pathological process that led to the defeat of the valve apparatus (rheumatism, infectious endocarditis, atherosclerosis, etc.)
- heart failure syndrome

Introduction:

Valve lesion syndrome:

- Direct signs of heart disease
 - sed by a violation of the function of the affected valve and a change in blood flow through it
 - auscultation of the heart (including special techniques)
 - change in tones, additional tones, noises and/or their equivalents
 - Foncg (FCG), Echocardiography (valve visualization, detection of regurgitation, an assessment of a transplited gradient), MRI, SKT, X -ray contact ventriculography.
- indirect signs of heart defect, the consequence of compensatory hypertrophy and/or dilatation of the heart chambers and blood flow disorders of dependent areas. Due to compensatory hypertrophy and/or dilatation of heart chambers and blood flow disorders in dependent areas
 - Physical methods (changes in heart tones, identification of hypertrophy and dilatation of the heart during examination, palpation and percussion),
 - ECG (hypertrophy of heart, rhythm disturbances),
 - chest radiography (enlargement of heart, signs of pulmonary hypertension, stagnation in the lungs),

- echocardiography (identification of hypertrophy of departments, assessment of the size of the heart chambers) - SKT, MRI

Direct signs of MS auscultation. Fong.

- S1 - loud clapping, MB weakened with complete loss of mobility of the sampler;
- OS-shift of the opening of MK-high-frequency tone ($S2-SOS = 0.05-0.12''$);
- quail rhythm;
- presystolic noise;
- protodiastolic noise (low -frequency, rumbling, decreasing);
- diastolic trembling (cat purring) at the top - the equivalent of protodiastolic noise;

Pathophysiology MS (1):

Outstation of blood flow from the HPD to LV to the diastole → overload of the HPD with pressure → concentric hypertrophy of the HPD:

Subjective symptoms (complaints)- no

Objectively: auscultation: direct signs of vice, percussion dimensions of the LPR are not changed (3 m/r on the left),

ECG: HALL HEARS - (p -Mitrale)

Echo kg: direct signs of vice + HPL hypertrophy

Pathophysiology MS (2-1):

↑ MS degree →

↑ atrijsen-ghost gradient (a-v grad) on MK

Oncentric GLPR Myogenic dilatation of the HPR →

→ Etrogrand increase in pulmonary venous and capillary pressure (J-receptors) (venous LH)

→ Restinal hypertension (LH) (passive / active)

Pathophysiology MS (2-2):

Subjective symptoms (depend on A-V Grad):

- Small A -V Grad -in rest there are no symptoms. At physical. load - bouts of shortness of breath, cough (LH). Heltering (LH).

- With an increase in A-V GRAD (RLPR $\geq$ 25mm HG) and LH-shortness of breath at rest, night paroxysmal shortness of breath, orthopic, pulmonary edema.

Objectively: signs of dilatation of the HPD, pulmonary hypertension.

- percussion: an increase in the boundaries of OST on the left in 3 m/r (LPR dilatation), in 2 m/r on the right (LA)

- auscultation: emphasis and bifurcation P2, signs of stagnation in the lungs (LH).

- Pulse: small content (fixed CB), atrial fibrillation (LPR dilatation),

- ECG: - P -Mitrale, atrial fibrillation (LPR dilatation)

- X-ray signs of UV-I HPR, pulmonary hypertension, stagnation in the lungs

- echocardiography - dilatation of the cavity of the KHR, a gradient of pressure on MK, an increase in pressure in the pulmonary artery

Pathophysiology MS (3)

Arterial pulmonary hypertension (active) →

Overloading with pancreatic pressure →

Concentric hypertrophy of pancreas →

At RL > 60 ↑ mm hg - myogenic dilatation of pancreas →

Signs of pancreas of SN, relative tricuspid

Subjective symptoms: weakness, fatigue at loads (fixed SV)

Objectively: signs of hypertrophy and dilatation of the pancreas (heart impetus, epigastric pulsation, uv-th AST)

- Signs of pancreas of SN (systemic venous hypertension, peripheral edema, hepatomegaly, ascites)

- Signs of tricuspid inhalers (pulsation of cervical veins, noise of 3 sash insufficiency, decrease in the severity of shortness of breath)

ECG: UV PPR (p-Pulmonale) and pancreas

X -ray signs of an increase in the right departments

Echocardiogram: hypertrophy and dilatation of the cavity of PPR and pancreas, tricuspid regurgitation

Mitral failure: auscultation (direct signs)

S1 is weakened;

S3 (increased blood flow through the mitral hole in the phase of quick filling of the LV) - with mitral failure, it may not be a sign of decompensation of SN;

Noise- (pan) systolic, merging with s1, -rytoid -fucker - -out -frequency -maxi at the top - radiation in the left axillar region;

Pathophysiology MN (1):

Retrograde blood flow in the LPR> Overloading with the volume of LPR → UV. Pressure in the LPR → eccentric hypertrophy/ myogenic dilatation of the HPR> Volumetric overload of LV ↓ eccentric GLG (Franca-Starling zone);

- Patients with moderate MN remain asymptomatic for many years
- Objectively: signs of eccentric hypertrophy of LV, LPR dilatation

Pathophysiology MN (2):

Volumetric overload of LV →

Eccentric GLG → ↑ → SV

Milegenic dilatation of LV →

Code of the LPD CDD KDD KDD →

Retrograndal prevailing pressure in the legend. Vienna and capillaries (LG Venous)

Symptoms of LV SN:

Subjective: shortness of breath at load, paroxysmal night shortness of breath, orthopnea, pulmonary edema;

Objectively: emphasis and bifurcation P2 (LH, shortening the phase of the exile of the LV); pulmonary venous stagnation/pulmonary hypertension (SN symptoms);

ECG: Hypertrophy of HPR and LV;

Radiography gr. Cells: Uv-E-E CHR and LV, stagnation in the lungs;

Pathophysiology MN (3):

LG venous → pulmonary arterial hypertension →

Overloading with pancreatic pressure →

Concentric hypertrophy/myogenic dilatation of the pancreas → General Davl-I in the PPR → Exceper. Hypertr/Dilatation PPR → Symptoms of PZ SN

Subjective symptoms: weakness, fatigue (SV) ↓

Objectively: signs of hypertrophy and dilatation of the pancreas (heart impetus, epigastric pulsation, uv-th AST)

Signs of pancreas of SN (systemic venous hypertension, peripheral edema, hepatomegaly, ascites, hydrotorax)

ECG, radiography of gr. Cells, echocardiography: signs of uv-me of the right departments (hypertrophy and dilatation of PPR and pancreas)

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